

TRANSIENT AIR PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENT OF FIBROUS REINFORCEMENT

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1 Fabric Air Permeability Assessment

Permeability of a fibrous reinforcement is an important physical parameter in Liquid Composite Molding (LCM). A great amount of effort has been spent on measuring such material property. Most of the techniques employed rely on liquid injection experiments. However permeability measurement using air instead of a liquid can provide a cleaner and faster measurement with reusable fabrics. To analyse the pressure drop along unfilled fabrics and the actual boundary condition at the flow front, it is necessary to understand how air flows through fabrics.

2 Modeling

The averaging method allows considering the porous medium as a continuous body; hence the conservation laws can be applied. For a fluid system, the general conservation equation is given by the following equation in the Eulerian frame [1],

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = \hat{\rho} \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\rho}$ is the rate at which mass is produced per unit volume of the system by chemical reactions or reduced by absorption for instance, ρ is the density and \mathbf{v} is the interstitial fluid velocity.

Considering air as a Newtonian fluid, the momentum conservation for the air flow across a porous medium may be described using Darcy's law, which is the simplest assumption in the form of a linear relationship between a flux and a driving force [2],

$$\mathbf{q} = -\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} (\nabla P - \rho \mathbf{g}) \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{q} is the filtration velocity or Darcy flux (discharge per unit area related to \mathbf{v} by porosity ϑ : $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{v}\vartheta$), \mathbf{g} the gravity acceleration, and ∇P the pressure gradient vector.

Combining Equation (1, 2) with the ideal gas law, considering one dimensional flow in a homogeneous medium and neglecting gravity (term $\rho \mathbf{g} = 0$) leads to the fundamental equation [3],

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = -\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\vartheta \mu} \nabla \cdot P \nabla P \quad (3)$$

The fundamental equation provides a fast method to back-calculate air permeability with the pressure data.

3 Experiment

3.1 Experimental set-up and measurement

The equipment to measure air permeability of the fibrous preform by one dimensional flow is shown in Fig. 1. A preform is inserted between a set of top and bottom platens, sealed with an o-ring seal. The outlet and inlet are respectively connected to a vacuum pump and the atmosphere and controlled by valves. Pressures P_1 and P_2 are monitored by pressure gauges and recorded by a data acquisition system.

For one-dimensional transient flow, the experiment begins by setting the initial pressure, corresponding to $t < 0$ in Eq.4. This is obtained by closing valve 2 and opening valve 1 until the values of P_1 and P_2 equilibrate exactly atmospheric pressure within the fabric. Then, a dropping pressure at the boundary 2 is applied while closing valve 1 and opening valve 2 to let the vacuum in, corresponding to $t > 0$ in Eq.4. During all the steps, $P_1(t)$ and $P_2(t)$ are recorded for further analysis. In conclusion, the boundary conditions are,

$$\begin{cases} P_1 = P_{atm}, \nabla P_2 = 0 & t < 0, \\ P_1 = P_2 = P_{atm} & \text{when } t = 0, \\ \nabla P_1 = 0, P_2 = P_{vac} & t > 0. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where P_{vac} is a vacuum pressure around 2000 Pa. The method is referred to as raised pressure method (DPM). Simulation is based on solving Eq.3 for P_1 , with boundary and initial conditions associated. $P_1(t)$ and $P_2(t)$ are recorded during experiments, and other parameters are determined: viscosity μ is calculated from environmental temperature T , and porosity of sample ϑ is provided by the sample thickness and areal weight. Then permeability K is estimated by minimizing the distance between experimental and simulated results obtained for $P_1(t)$, under the prescribed experimental pressure $P_2(t)$. The experiment could also begin with vacuum initial pressure and then a raised pressure is applied as one boundary condition,

$$\begin{cases} P_1 = P_{vac}, \nabla P_2 = 0 & t < 0, \\ P_1 = P_2 = P_{vac} & \text{when } t = 0, \\ \nabla P_1 = 0, P_2 = P_{atm} & t > 0. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

which is referred to as raised pressure method, or RPM.

3.2 Boundary condition modification

The boundary condition is considered to be zero flux when the corresponding valve is closed. Since air is compressible, the air trapped between the valve and the side of fabric, shown in Fig. 2, may cause a slight flux at the boundary when pressure is changing. Assuming a quasi-static flow, the trapped air shares same values of pressure, density and temperature. For the points $x = 0$ and $x = L$, mass conservation gives,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} V + \rho A v = 0 & x = 0 \\ \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} V - \rho A v = 0 & x = L \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where V is the volume of air trapped, A is the sectional area for air flow, and L is the length of the fabric sample. Combining with an ideal gas law and Darcy's law, boundary condition could be obtained in terms of P ,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{K}{\vartheta \mu} P \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} \frac{V}{A} = 0 & x = 0 \\ \frac{K}{\vartheta \mu} P \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} \frac{V}{A} = 0 & x = L \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where the volume area ratio V/A is the dominant parameter. For a set of experimental P_1 and P_2 , the permeability obtained by back-calculation could change remarkably with different volume area ratio. The variation of calculated permeability can be estimated as,

$$\frac{K}{K_0} = 1 + 2 \frac{V}{AL} \quad (8)$$

where K_0 is the permeability obtained from back-calculation with unmodified boundary conditions. This empirical relationship is confirmed by sets of experiments on different materials, shown in Fig. 3. Since V/A is around 0.1 in our experiments, leading to 100% difference in permeability, it's important to apply the real boundary condition considering the air trapped in the setup.

4 Materials and Results

4.1 Glass twill-weave fabric

The air transient measurements are carried out for various volume fractions. Results show that permeability has a similar trend as those extracted from liquid compression tests, [4] (Fig. 4). DPM and RPM have been applied to a glass twill-weave perform at various fiber volume fraction, and results shown in and Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 give very similar in-plane permeability, $5.4 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$ and $5.9 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$ respectively, with a standard-deviation lower than 10% for 7 sets of experiments with different flow rates. Although measurements on the same fabric under various loading patterns, such as a raised pressure or a dropping pressure, give close value, permeability is quite sensitive to the structure of fabric and the trapped air volume at boundary.

4.2 Carbon twill-weave fabric

Raised and dropping pressure measurements are carried out on Carbon G986 twill weave, 6 plies at 0° orientation, with volume fraction at 44.2%, 48.6% and 54.9%. Permeabilities obtained by transient air flow measurement are compared with liquid compression measurements [4], and the differences are close to the error of measurements, shown in Fig. 7. Simulations of flow based on Darcy's law fits well with experimental data, shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9.

5 Conclusions

A methodology to measure fabric in-plane permeability using a transient air flow has been described. The results match well the permeability measured with liquid compression and injection techniques. The method, based on the simple measurement of gas pressure throughout the transient flow, is convenient, clean and fast, avoids usage of a gas flow meter and offers a way to further study the air transport within porous media.

Fig. 1. One dimensional experimental set-up for air permeability measurement

Fig. 2. Air trapped between valve, platens and preform

Fig. 3. Variation of permeability obtained by back-calculation using different volume area ratio, based on experimental pressures for three types of fabrics: 3D glass fabric, glass twill-weave fabric, carbon twill-weave fabric

Fig. 4. Comparison of permeability K obtained by transient air flow measurement and liquid compression measurement and liquid unidirectional injection measurement method on glass woven fabric with different volume fraction V_f [4] .

Fig. 5. Comparison between experimental and computed P_1 for the glass twill-weave fabric at 51% fibre volume fraction, back calculated K equals $5.4 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$

Fig. 6. Comparison between experimental and computed P_1 for glass twill-weave preform at 51% fibre volume fraction, back calculated K equals $5.9 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$

Fig. 7. Comparison of permeability K obtained by transient air flow measurement and liquid compression measurement on carbon woven fabric with different volume fraction V_f [4].

Fig. 8. Comparison between experimental and computed P_1 in raised pressure measurement for carbon twill-weave preform at 48.6% fibre volume fraction, $K = 3.65 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 9. Comparison between experimental and computed P_1 in dropping pressure measurement for carbon twill-weave preform at 48.6% fibre volume fraction, $K = 3.60 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$.

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